

SUPPORTING INFORMATION FOR “REMODELING MALE COERCION AND THE EVOLUTION OF SEXUAL AUTONOMY BY MATE CHOICE”

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES S1-S5

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Figure S1. Results of numerical simulations of the model for the persistence of the male autonomy-enhancing trait (B_2) through the full parameter space explored for this study. Color represents the final frequency of the B_2 allele at equilibrium. Parameter sets are: $a_r=\{4, 8, 12, 16\}$, $c=\{0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}$, $s_r=0.1$, $s_b=0.1$, $u=0.1$, $s_r=0.01$, $a_b=0$ to 20 at increments of 0.1, and $\gamma=0$ to 1 at increments of 0.01.

Figure S2. Results of low-mutation ($u=0.01$) version of numerical simulations of the model for the persistence of the male autonomy-enhancing trait (B_2). Color represents the final frequency of the B_2 allele at equilibrium. Parameter sets are: $a_i=\{4, 8, 12, 16\}$, $c=\{0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8\}$, $s_r=0.1$, $s_b=0.1$, $s_r=0.001$, $a_b=0$ to 20 at increments of 0.1, and $\gamma=0$ to 1 at increments of 0.01. Note that the lower mutation rate alters the window for possible parameter ranges for our simulations (see Appendix S2), so the range of values for c explored differ somewhat from Figure S1.

Figure S3. Allele-frequency-by-generation-time representations of the numerical simulation data presented in Figure 2A. (A) Results for the $\gamma=0$ scenario. (B) Results for the $\gamma=0.8$ scenario.

Figure S4. Relationship between the approximate magnitude of the genetic correlation between the B_2 and R_2 alleles (D_{BR}) at quasi-linkage equilibrium and the magnitude of the effectiveness of the protection associated with the male autonomy-enhancing trait (γ) across values of the attractiveness of the male autonomy-enhancing trait (a_b ; panel A), and across values of the likelihood of successful coercion (c , panel B). Approximation derived from our weak selection approximation analysis (File S4). Other parameter values for panel A are: $c=0.001$, $a_t=0.002$, $s_t=0.001$, $s_b=0.001$, $u=0.0001$, $s_r=0.00001$, $r_2=b_2=0.5$. Parameter values for panel B are the same except a_b is held constant at 0.005. In each instance, $t_2=\hat{t}_2$, as dictated by the combination of the other parameters (See Appendix S2 and File S4).

Figure S5. Supplemental data associated with the numerical simulation results presented in Figure 4. (A) Allele-frequency-by-generation-time representations data presented in Figure 4. (B) Corresponding genetic-correlation-by-generation-time results for the same numerical simulations. Note that the x-axis limits for generation times have variable scales.